

On the eigenvalues of the Magick Operator

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Abstract

In this paper, the properties of the operator $\hat{M}$ are explored, building upon the previously established algebraic foundation[1]. The focus is on events with two outcomes labelled $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$. The eigenvalue problem for the operator $\hat{M}_n$ is considered, and the operator's action on other states is investigated. Spectral decomposition is employed, leading to a linear combination representation of the operator.

The paper also examines the effect of multiple Magick operators acting on the same state. The commutation relations between these operators are analysed, revealing interesting properties. Specifically, if the outcomes are uncorrelated or have the same magnitude, the commutator is zero.

The interaction between multiple intents is studied, and a fundamental result is obtained: the total eigenvalue of an eigenvector for multiple intents is the product of individual eigenvalues, akin to a superposition-like effect observed in nature. The order of intents is shown to be unimportant when generated simultaneously during a probabilistic event.

The paper outlines future research directions, including analysing the correlation coefficient s , decomposing the operator $\hat{M}$ into infinitesimal operators, and investigating the dynamical equation of state evolution under $\hat{M}$ operators.

1 Introduction

The previous publication[1] laid the groundwork with a basic algebraic foundation. In this paper, we delve into the properties of the operator $\hat{M}$ while also exploring the effects of multiple operators acting on the same state.

2 Representations of the $\hat{M}$ operator

This investigation focuses solely on events with two outcomes, labelled $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$. The eigenvalue problem for the operator $\hat{M}_n$ is defined as:

$$\hat{M}_n |n\rangle = m_n |n\rangle \tag{1}$$

To gain comprehensive insights into the operator $\hat{M}$, its action on other states must be examined. By selecting $\hat{M}_1$ as the operator, and knowing the value of

$m_1 a_1^2$, we can deduce that, after the operator acts on the state, the resulting probability must equate to 1:

$$\hat{M}_1 |2\rangle = \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} |2\rangle \quad (2)$$

2.1 Spectral decomposition

For generalization, we consider correlated states $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$, where $s \in \mathbb{C}$ denotes the correlation coefficient with $|s|^2 \in (0, 1]$.

$$0 \neq \langle 1|2\rangle = s \in \mathbb{C} : |s|^2 \in (0, 1] \quad (3)$$

Under this axiom, the operator $\hat{M}_1$ can be expressed as a linear combination of projection operators:

$$\hat{M}_1 = m_1 (|1\rangle \langle 1| + s^* |2\rangle \langle 1|) + \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} (|2\rangle \langle 2| + s |1\rangle \langle 2|) \quad (4)$$

Equivalently, in matrix notation:

$$M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 & \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} s \\ m_1 s^* & \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

3 Multiple Magick operators acting on the same state

Suppose two sources seek to increase the probability of state $|1\rangle$. Their respective operators are $\hat{M}_1$ and $\hat{M}_2$, given in matrix form as:

$$M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 & \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} s \\ m_1 s^* & \frac{1 - m_1 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$M_2 = \begin{pmatrix} m_2 & \frac{1 - m_2 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} s \\ m_2 s^* & \frac{1 - m_2 a_1^2}{1 - a_1^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Multiplying these matrices yields the combined effect of both sources on the state. The non-commutative nature of matrices generally poses a problem, but focusing on the event where one intention occurs before another, specifically $\hat{M}_1$ acting before $\hat{M}_2$, provides valuable insights:

$$M_2 \cdot M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 m_2 + \frac{m_1 (m_2 a_1^2 - 1) |s|^2}{a_1^2 - 1} & \frac{(m_1 a_1^2 - 1) (2 m_2 a_1^2 - m_2 - 1) s}{(a_1^2 - 1)^2} \\ \frac{m_1 s^* (2 m_2 a_1^2 - m_2 - 1)}{a_1^2 - 1} & \frac{((m_2 a_1^2 - m_2) |s|^2 + m_2 a_1^2 - 1) (m_1 a_1^2 - 1)}{(a_1^2 - 1)^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The operator $\hat{M}_{21} \equiv \hat{M}_2 \hat{M}_1$ possesses the following expectation value in the eigenvector $|1\rangle$ representation:

$$\langle 1 | \hat{M}_{21} | 1 \rangle = m_1 m_2 + \frac{m_1 (m_2 a_1^2 - 1) |s|^2}{a_1^2 - 1} \quad (9)$$

3.1 Commutation relations

From the foregoing, it is evident that $\hat{M}_2$ and $\hat{M}_1$ do not commute. The commutator of these operators takes the form of the following matrix:

$$\left[\hat{M}_1, \hat{M}_2 \right] = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{|s|^2 (m_1 - m_2)}{a_1^2 - 1} & -\frac{s(m_1 - m_2)}{a_1^2 - 1} \\ \frac{s^* (m_1 - m_2)}{a_1^2 - 1} & -\frac{|s|^2 (m_1 - m_2)}{a_1^2 - 1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Two intriguing properties arise from the commutator operator:

1. If the outcomes are uncorrelated (independent), the commutator is zero.
2. If both intents have the same magnitude, the commutator is zero.

The second conclusion is self-evident, as intents with equal magnitudes are indistinguishable. However, the first conclusion requires further analysis.

3.2 $\hat{M}_{21}$ acting on independent states

When the states are uncorrelated, i.e., $s = 0$, the eigenvalue of the operator $\hat{M}_{21}$ for the eigenstate $|1\rangle$ is given by:

$$\hat{M}_{21} |1\rangle = m_{12} |1\rangle = m_1 \cdot m_2 |1\rangle \quad (11)$$

This fundamental result provides an interpretation of outcomes generated by multiple intents: the total eigenvalue of an eigenvector resulting from multiple intents is the product of individual eigenvalues, as if the intents are unaware of each other. This phenomenon resembles a superposition-like effect observed in various natural phenomena. Furthermore, if intents are generated simultaneously during a probabilistic event, the order of intents becomes irrelevant, owing to the commutative nature of the operators governing these intents.

4 Discussion

The following aspects remain to be analyzed:

1. The nature and properties of the correlation coefficient s .
2. The possibility of representing the operator $\hat{M}$ as a composition of infinitesimal operators $\hat{\mu}_1, \hat{\mu}_2, \dots, \hat{\mu}_n$ acting on an eigenstate – essentially decomposing the operator into a sequence of operators acting on the state at different time intervals.
3. The possible dynamical equation governing the evolution of states when an $\hat{M}$ operator acts on them – the representation of $\hat{M}$ operators in time.

References

- [1] Leonardo C. Olyachim. On the algebraic treatment of chaos magick theory, July 2023.